

Piloting the **ENCORE+** Quality Framework

Piloting the ENCORE+ Quality Framework

ENCORE+ deliverable D.5.3

European Network for Catalysing
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Executive summary

This report provides the results of the evaluation of the ENCORE+ Quality Transparency Framework (ENCORE QTF). The QTF enables repositories to make their quality practices visible and explicit, and is described in ENCORE+ deliverable D5.2. The QTF was developed through extensive consultation with the OER community as part of the activities of the ENCORE+ project. The report provides the results of the evaluation of the ENCORE+ Quality Transparency Framework (ENCORE QTF). This instrument enables repositories to make their quality practices visible and explicit, and is described in ENCORE+ deliverable D5.2. The QTF was developed through extensive consultation with the OER community as part of the activities of the ENCORE+ project. The two main purposes of the QTF are to make the quality practice of an OER repository visible to users (e.g. learners and teachers), and to enable repositories to share and jointly develop their quality practices on the base of and through a shared metadata framework.

The evaluation reengages with the OER community to establish if the QTF that emerged from the consultation process meets their expectations and requirements. Six extended interviews were carried out with representatives of repositories. The interviews were carried out remotely by a representative of the ENCORE+ project. Each interviewee completed the QTF for their own repository, and responded to questions about the QTF. The results were documented by the interviewer summarising the interviewees' responses during the interview and entering them into the shared document.

The results show that completion of the QTF form did not present any substantial challenges to any of the interviewees. However, a number of improvements were identified and the QTF has been adapted in response to these findings. Respondents were positive about the opportunities presented by the QTF for increasing the transparency of repositories' QA practices. Transparency offers were seen as, firstly, a measure that could increase trust in repositories and their contents, and secondly as a means of sharing practice between repositories, and providing a resource for the development of individual repositories QA practices. Some respondents also saw the QTF as a possible route to an OER repository quality mark or badge. The results of the evaluation also provide a useful starting point for the design of an infrastructure to support the sharing of QA processes between repositories and for repository stakeholders. A potential constraint on the adoption of such an infrastructure is that the QTF is not, at present, equally appropriate for all types of repositories.

1. Introduction

This deliverable reports on the evaluation of the ENCORE+ Quality Transparency Framework (ENCORE+ QTF). This instrument responds to the utmost importance of the requirement “to enable repositories to make their quality practices visible and explicit”¹, as described in ENCORE+ deliverable D5.2. The QTF was developed through extensive consultation with the OER community as part of the activities of the ENCORE+ project. These activities included four TPG workshops that “were designed to outline the current situation of quality in OER repositories”² and showed clearly that “there could not be a 'one size fits all' approach for the quality of OER repositories.”³ Therefore, “the aim was to develop a framework that can be made available to repositories to make their quality transparent to users and other repositories, instead of standardizing quality assurance as such.”⁴ Benchmark categories were developed by experts in order to describe different quality approaches.⁵

In this evaluation we again engage with the OER community to establish whether the QTF which has emerged from the consultation process meets their expectations and requirements. Consistent with project methodology, we achieve this through six extended interviews with representatives of repositories. The process followed in this evaluation was established in D5.2., and here we report on its implementation and the results which were achieved.

¹ Ehlers, U.-D., Schmidbauer, F. „Building the ENCORE+ Quality Transparency Framework (ENCORE QTF)” (2022), p. 9. <https://encoreproject.eu/2022/11/22/quality-transparency-in-oer-repositories/>

² *ibid.*, p. 9.

³ *ibid.*, p. 11.

⁴ *ibid.*, p. 11.

⁵ *ibid.*, p. 11.

2. Method

2.1 Objectives

The purpose of the pilot reported here is set out on page 23-24 of ENCORE+ D5.2 <https://encoreproject.eu/2022/11/22/quality-transparency-in-oer-repositories/>, and paraphrased here. The objective of the pilots is pragmatic: to test and assess the QTF with OER repositories. This involves examining the capacity of the QTF to meet its three main purposes, i.e. to:

- make the quality practice of an OER repository visible to users, e.g. learners and teachers.
- enable repositories to share and jointly develop their quality practices on the base of a shared Quality Transparency Framework.
- enable repositories to assess their quality practice according to the framework and further develop quality assurance mechanisms mentioned in the framework categories.

The results of the pilot assess the need for refinements to the Quality Transparency Framework and make proposals for improvements.

2.2 Ethical approval

The research was approved by the Comité de Ética de la Investigación (Research Ethics Committee) de La Universidad Internacional de La Rioja, with the code P1004_2023. An informed consent document (Appendix 1) was sent to the respondent prior to the interview, and returned to the interviewer with a digital signature from the interviewees business email account.

2.3 Procedure

Remote interviews were carried out with repository representatives in which the interviewee completed the QTF for their own repository and responded to questions about the QTF. The QTF was prepared as an instrument presented as an editable shared document, with check boxes and areas for free text responses. A separate copy of this document was prepared for each interview, enabling both the interviewee and the evaluator to see and edit the document at the same time, and to complete the framework together. The results were documented by the interviewer summarising the interviewees' responses during the interview and entering them into the shared

document. For each element of the QTF, responses and feedback were documented as a comment in the table. After completing the QTF, the interviewees were asked a standard set of questions regarding the QTF and were invited to provide free feedback. The interviewee had access to the document during the interview to ensure that responses were correctly collected, and also had the opportunity to review their answers once the data had been gathered.

- 1) Please provide feedback on the overall concept of the QTF.
 - a) Do you find the QTF overall useful for making the quality of your OER repository transparent to users and other repositories? What could be improved?
 - b) What do you as a repository need from a tool to make your quality practice transparent?
- 2) Please provide feedback on the overall experience you had completing the framework.
 - 1) How easy or hard was it to fill in the form for your repository?
 - 2) Which were barriers or enablers for completing it?
 - 3) How will applying the QTF to your OER repository incite you to develop your quality practice?
- 3) Please provide feedback on the level of detail.
 - a) Which new (sub)categories are needed to describe the quality practice that are currently missing in the framework?
 - b) Which questions can be merged/dropped?
 - c) Which questions are unclear and need to be better defined?
- 4) Please provide feedback on the target group.
 - a) Which target group is the QTF helpful for?
 - b) Would you differentiate the QTF for different user groups (e.g. autonomous learners, producers of OER, teachers, ...)? Name the user groups you would differentiate the QTF for.
- 5) Please freely give feedback on the QTF and your experience with it.
 - a) Is there anything else you want to add?

2.4 Respondents

Name	Country	Repository	Date
Marcell Varkonyi	Netherlands	Open Textbooks	9th February 2023
Marco Timm	Germany	Wirlernen	6th March 2023
Martin Ebner	Austria	TU GRAZ	8th March
Margreta Tveisme	Norway	Norwegian Digital Learning Arena (NDLA)	23rd March 2023
Wiebke Breustedt	Germany	Open Resources Campus NRW (ORCA.nrw)	23rd March 2023
Olimpius Istrate	Romania	Digitaledu	7th July 2023

3. Results

3.1 Range of repository types in the responses

[TU Delft Open Textbooks](#) (henceforth 'Open Textbooks') has a publishing model for academic books and textbooks for use in higher education. It responds to authors requests for Open Publishing. Open books go through peer review. Open textbooks are not peer reviewed, but are published by experts and actively used in education. Students are part of the quality control process, providing feedback on the material, with unofficial feedback colleagues. Feedback may lead to a new edition.

[Wirlernen](#) hosts open educational resources for the whole range of the German education system. There is a well-established and documented review process, carried out by staff and volunteers from the community.

[TU GRAZ](#) is an institutional repository of open educational resources for Higher Education run by the University of Graz and federated with the national Austrian repository. The quality process is based on mandatory training for all contributors to the repository.

[Norwegian Digital Learning Arena \(NDLA\)](#) has an editorial model, employing teachers to make resources for use in schools. The authors are provided with extensive documentation on quality control procedures.

[Open Resources Campus NRW \(ORCA.nrw\)](#) provides services to a consortium of 37 public universities and colleges in North Rhine-Westphalia and was established in 2021. ORCA.nrw has a quality process that is managed by the central repository, guidelines, and provides support for authors. The quality process is still under development.

[Digitaledu](#) is a user generated repository for schoolteachers in Romania. It is linked to the **iTeach** platform, from which 2300 teachers upload their OERs to the repository, and also to the Ministry of Education, which certifies the resources for use in schools.

3.2 Responses to the fields of the QTF

In this section we discuss the responses of the informants in relation to each field of the QTF

In no case did any of the respondents find that they were unable to provide data for any of the questions in the QTF form.

3.2.1 Quality practice

Short description of quality practice

Please summarize in a few sentences or bullet points the quality practice for your OER repository.

Repository	Assessment
Open Textbooks	No difficulties in understanding or responding. 111 word description provided. No link to repository QA process.
Wirlernen	No difficulties in understanding or responding. 130 word description provided. Two links provided
TU GRAZ	No difficulties in understanding or responding. Link to academic paper describing the training process. 131 word description provided.
NDLA	No difficulties in understanding or responding. No link provided, perhaps because the documentation is internal. 173 word description provided.
ORCA.nrw	No difficulties in understanding or responding. No links provided, because the QA process has not been finalised. 178 word description provided.
Digitaledu	No difficulties in understanding or responding, but the institutional relationships of the repository with the teacher platform and with the Ministry of Education are complex to explain. 394 word description provided.

Findings:

- No problems identified with this field
- The material in the links was relevant and informative. Not all repositories have this material available, and the QTF could offer a convenient way to present QA information.

Quality methods in use

Actors involved in quality development	Open Textbooks	Wir Lernen	TU Graz	NDLA	ORCA.nrw	Digital -edu	Total
Peer review of new resources (unpaid)		X				X	2
Peer review of new resources (paid)		X		X			2
Periodic expert review of repository		X	X	X			3
User ranking/rating of OER				X		X	2
Author identification/validation	X			X	X	X	4
Quality-check of meta-data	X	X	X	X	X	X	6
Application of standardized quality criteria to assess OER		X	X	X	X	X	5
Collecting user feedback in the repository							0
Quality through connection to and reputation of institution	X				X	X	3
Technical quality parameters (e.g. permanent URL of OER)	X	X	X	X	X		5
Other:	X	X					2

Findings:

- The spread of selections was not overly concentrated. Only one item was selected by all informants, and only one was not selected by any informant, with contrasting profiles between repositories. The *Quality methods in use* item therefore successfully represents differences between the QTF approaches of repositories.
- Some informants wanted to add comments about their selections. These could be added in the field to the right, but the comments are not linked to the item, with consequent potential for confusion. Some way of linking the comments to the checkboxes should be provided, if only an instruction to mention the item, with numbering of the items to make this more convenient. In an implementation of the framework, links should be provided to a comment field for each item. The field should accept web links.
- *Other*: The informants who selected *Other* described feedback from evaluation forms for courses in which the resource was used (open textbooks), and *AI processes* (WirLernen). These items could be considered for inclusion in the list of options. In particular AI should be included.

Related quality instruments

Actors involved in quality development	Open Textbooks	Wir Lernen	TU Graz	NDLA	ORCA.nrw	Digital -edu	Total
Author training			X	X	X	X	4
Guidelines for content creation		X		X	X	X	4
Checklist	X	X	X	X	X	X	6
Questionnaire			X				1
Handbook		X	X	X	X		4
Benchmarks							0
AI		X					1
Meta data	X	X	X		X	X	5
Other:	X			X			2

Findings:

- The selections were distributed, with one of the items being selected by all informants, and one item with no selections, with contrasting profiles between repositories. The *related quality instruments* item therefore successfully represents differences between the QTF approaches of repositories.
- The only item which was not selected by any informants was *Benchmarks*. Two informants were not clear what this meant in the context of QA.
 - The interviewer clarified that it referred to “a statistical basis for a decision to delete a resource or not (used in past five years, satisfaction rating of 4.3... etc.)”. It would be helpful to add a clarification on these lines.
- The *Other* item was selected by two informants: Open Textbook (Copyright and similarity check with software and by colleagues) and NDLA (interviews with the people who start working for the repository).
 - It is proposed that ‘compliance check with software’ is added to the list of options.
- One informant questioned whether ‘AI’ is a method. It is suggested that this is made more specific, and ‘AI-driven. It would be more appropriate for ‘AI’ to be a method
 - It is recommended that this item be moved to 1.2.
- In 1.2 the term ‘meta-data’ is used. In 1.2.1 this is given as ‘meta data’. The more generally used spelling is ‘metadata’.
 - it is recommended that the QTF standardises on ‘metadata’.

Actors involved in quality development

Actors involved in quality development	Open Textbooks	Wir Lernen	TU Graz	NDLA	ORCA.nrw	Digital -edu	Total
User (Teacher)	X	X	X	X		X	5
User (Learner)		X	X	X			3
User (Librarian)			X				1
User (Author)	X	X	X		X	X	5
User (OER provider)		X	X		X		3
User (Other...)							0
Official (Editorial Board Member)		X				X	2
Official (CEO)			X	X			2
Official (Manager)			X				1
Official (Quality Manager)		X	X	X	X		4
Official (Researcher)		X	X			X	3
Official (Policy maker)	X		X				2
Official (Developer)		X	X	X			3
Official (Technology / infrastructure provider)	X	X	X	X			4
Official (AI)		X					1
Official (Other...)					X		1
Other:							0

Findings:

- The selections were effectively distributed, with none of the items being selected by all informants, and all except 'other' being chosen by at least one informant. This results in contrasting profiles between repositories, and

therefore the *Actors involved in quality development* item successfully represents differences between the QTF approaches of repositories.

- All respondents made use of the free text box to the right of the checklist, and all but one raised questions about the meaning of an item on the checklist.
- **Open Textbooks** commented that they themselves are the infrastructure provider, and that in their case the user and the teacher are often the same person.
- **Wirlernen** asked for a definition of an ‘official’, and also said that they have a “designated role to see how AI can support the process”. This raises the issue that it is not defensible to present AI as an ‘actor’. Rather it is a technology which is deployed by a developer, or perhaps in future directly by a quality manager. In the case of
- **TU Graz**, the system is part of the library department, so librarians are the officials.
- **NDLA** commented that they have “a team leader for the different people making the resources, team leader for the testing and UX quality, team leader for counselling and support. It’s hard to place them into the categories”. Moreover the authors in NDLA are ‘official’, in that they are paid by the repository.
- **ORCA.nrw** raised a question about what ‘development’ means here, whether it refers to the specification of the quality, or the incremental quality improvement of the resources. The ‘developer’ role could also refer to a developer of infrastructure.
- **Digitaledu** commented that “the author is the teacher”.
- It is recommended that
 - The range of possible actors and their relationships is very wide and cannot be captured entirely in a single checklist. Nevertheless, the informants did not have major difficulties in characterising the repositories with the checklist. In order to achieve clarity, informants should be actively guided to make use of the free text field to explain how the roles in the checklist map onto their own circumstances. This should include the guidance that when teachers are also authors, both boxes should be ticked.
 - The term ‘official’ should be reconsidered, as it can suggest someone with regulatory or policing powers. It is proposed that ‘Staff’ would be clearer.

- The term ‘developer’ should be qualified to indicate what they are developing. The assumption of the evaluators is that this refers to ‘Repository developer’ and the field has been changed accordingly, but this should be checked with the authors of the QTF.

3.2.2 Information about your repository

Target group

All the informants were able to provide a clear statement of their target group.

Findings: no issues were identified

Legal requirements.

Findings:

- **NDLA** commented that they do not collect data about their users, and that this simplifies GDPR issues. This raises the issue that if the QTF is representing legal requirements, then it should also have a section explaining what data is gathered about the users and how it is managed. ORCA.nrw reported that they use Shibboleth (SSO service) to confirm that uploads are made by people who are actually teachers in the universities that are members of the consortium. This is also an aspect of identity management.
 - It is proposed that a new section be introduced on ‘Personal data’
- **ORCA.nrw** asked why legal requirements are part of the QTF, as the answer will always be “we fulfil all our legal obligations”. The rationale given by the interviewer was that this enables comparison between jurisdictions.
 - A note has been added in the instructions. This rationale should also be considered in introductory briefings to the QTF.
- It is confusing that the ‘description’ column contains N.A., which suggests that the question is not applicable.
 - It is recommended that N.A should be deleted, and the cell left blank in the description column.

Repository Languages

Findings: no issues were identified. The distinction between interface language (2.3) and content language (2.4) was clear

OER language

Findings: No issues were identified. This is a non-mandatory field, but all the informants provided the requested information.

3.3.3 Further aspects

Findings: two of the informants provided brief comments in this field. This indicates (a) that it is worth maintaining the field (b) that the questions of the QTF are comprehensive.

3.3.4 Additional services and characteristics

Community integration

Findings:

- All informants provided information about the communities that they work with. They also provided details about the roles and activities which support community integration, although that was not requested in the question or example. As this information is valuable and was made available by all informants, the text of the item should be expanded to explicitly elicit this information.
 - **It is recommended that** the guidance text is expanded to provide additional prompts: “What brings your community together? Does your repository have roles or activities to support the community? What kind of participation in the repository processes (if any) do you offer to community members?”

Credentialing

Findings:

- None of the repositories offered microcredentials (a finding which is in line with the ENCORE+ report on Credentialing and Open Educational Resources). However, the informants all had something to contribute to this field in terms of badges or recognition for users or authors, or in one case the relationship with MOOCs. It is therefore worth maintaining this field as it stands.

3.3.5 Organizational Data.

All informants completed this section without raising any issues.

3.3 Responses to follow up questions

1: Please provide feedback on the overall concept of the QTF.

1.a: Do you find the QTF overall useful for making the quality of your OER repository transparent to users and other repositories? What could be improved?

All the respondents said that they found the QTF to be useful. However, within this general finding each repository had a different perspective.

Two were particularly enthusiastic.

- Istrate (Digitaledu) said “I have been waiting for this for a long time”. Digitaledu is a mature repository, with many resources to share, and Istrate expressed the hope that “Our repository could be integrated with other similar libraries at local level and in other countries if we had better sharing of interoperability information about the structure of the library.”
- Breustedt (ORCA.nrw) found the QTF useful for an opposite reason: “I found it very useful. Right now we are setting up our QA system, and it includes the main processes and actors”.

Two found the QTF useful, but with provisos.

- Ebner (TU Graz) said “The instrument has a role, because ... if you violate copyright law you have to pay for it. And that is why we need the QA process. Transparency gets awareness of the reason why we are doing this.” However, he added “...it is very very hard to make it visible. Typically people don’t read things.”
- Timm (Wirlernen) said that he “would like to know what quality framework other repositories use”, but would like additional information (see below)

Two found the QTF useful, but felt that the profile of their repositories limited its relevance.

- Varkonyi (Open Textbooks) said “Most of the questions are relevant to ensuring OER quality. On the other hand ... the stakeholders you seem to be interested in are not necessarily ours. We are working with our university, which is big but local. For us, working with the teachers we know is enough of a mark of quality. We have ambitions to reach out beyond, but that is not something that (we) should manage.”

- Tveisme (NDLA) explained that NDLA commissions content from known schoolteachers, which is “...not the common way for a repository to be organised and driven. So the questions are more relevant for a conventional repository.” However, she added that “making the quality processes transparent is very useful”.

Timm (Wirlernen) said “For me it would be interesting to separate quality for content and quality for metadata. This is increasingly important if you want to share between repositories, how metadata are documented.” He also requested a section on how an institution’s quality framework was developed (e.g. based on published research, on standards, on the community’s ideas, etc.).

On the content side, Istrate (Digitaledu) said “...thinking pragmatically of the needs of the teachers. I would like to see some pedagogical criteria For example, this resource is about consolidation, or understanding...”

1.b: What do you as a repository need from a tool to make your quality practice transparent?

Five respondents indicated that making quality practices visible across repositories was their main need. Tveisme (NDLA) said that “making everything visible is a good approach”. Timm (Wirlernen) said that “More standardised terms to describe quality across repositories, a terminology that everyone agrees” would be useful. Ebner (TU Graz) said that “Comparison between repository QA would be useful”, and also that “On a technical level it would be nice to have APIs to validate against, so ‘my repository is following those guidelines’, providing the metadata over the API, and the tool certifies that the data is provided and available”. Breusted (ORCA.nrw) requested a tool that could be integrated in a website “appealing to users, in terms of visualisation and colours, without a high level of information density”. She also stressed the learning opportunities for repositories offered by the QTF and by the practice of other repositories. Istrate (Digitaledu) requested a public score card with information about the provider and the responsibility that they take for their content.

Varkonyi (Open Textbooks), in line with his response to the previous question, stressed the importance of “Clear ... transparent and traceable versioning of materials”, adding that “peer review, feedback from students is very valuable, also from teachers”.

Findings for post-QTF completion, question 1:

It should be remembered that these results are based on a small, expert sample, but they provide a clear indication that:

- The QTF is perceived as being useful by repository personnel.
- Not all respondents are equally enthusiastic, varying with the fit of the QTF to the purpose and maturity of the repository.
- Valorisation of the QTF would therefore depend on identifying a group of repositories with sufficiently strong motivation to be the first adopters, creating a demonstrator that could bring less committed repositories on board.
- The concept of quality, and its dimensions, remains a matter for debate. Future revisions of the QTF could consider placing some or all of the following aspects in separate categories: content; metadata; pedagogy.
- Respondents would welcome an infrastructure for comparison between QTF profiles. A range of suggestions was made, which provide a useful starting point for consideration of the design dimensions, but not a sufficient basis for making a recommendation for infrastructure.

2. Please provide feedback on the overall experience you had completing the framework.

2.a: Please provide feedback on the overall experience you had completing the framework.

On a five-point scale from “very hard” to “very easy”, four respondents chose the middle value, with one choosing ‘hard’ and one ‘very easy’.

Breustedt (ORCA.nrw) said that gathering the necessary information from the multiple colleagues involved in the QA process was the difficulty, rather than filling in the form.

The ‘hard’ response was from Tveisme (NDLA), who commented that this was “[b]ecause we have a model that is not what was in mind when the form was made. I had to adapt all the time. But that doesn’t mean that it is a bad form in any way”. Similarly, Varkonyi (Open Textbooks) said that the QTF is not “tailored to us as a stakeholder”. He suggested that taking into consideration the variety of resources (including textbooks, interactive textbooks, courses, microcredentials...) would help to “textbook, interactive textbooks, courses, microcredentials”.

Istrate (Digitaledu), who found the form ‘very easy’, would have found it “easier in Romanian”.

2.b: Which were barriers or enablers for completing it?

Timm (Wirlernen) mentioned the questions about metadata as a barrier, and did not find the term ‘official’ easy to understand. It is proposed that ‘staff’ would be clearer.

Considering 2.a and 2.b together, it should be noted that the form was filled out with the support of the researcher, and nevertheless most of the respondents did not find it easy to complete. Three respondents (Tveisme (NDLA), Timm (Wirlernen) and Ebner (TU Graz) said that the support of the interviewer had helped them to complete the form. Tveisme, who found the form ‘hard’ to complete, said “It is very good that we can have a conversation. It would take a lot more time if I was not able to clarify and ask, that we can talk our way through it.”

2.c: How will applying the QTF to your OER repository incite you to develop your quality practice?

Tveisme (NDLA) and Varkonyi (Open Textbooks), both of whom felt that the QTF did not address their repository profile, did not see ways to apply the QTF.

Breustedt (ORCA.nrw) found the structure of the form very helpful and would “consider looking at the check boxes further” in developing their own QA process.

The other three respondents stressed the need for transparency and communication of QA processes between repositories.

Findings for post-QTF completion, question 2:

- The QTF form is usable as it stands.
- The design of the form can be improved, and suggestions have been gathered. However, the principal challenges are not related to form design, but rather to the intellectual difficulty of relating complex local QA processes to a standard framework, suggesting that the QTF may be most effectively deployed in the interview-based format used in this evaluation.
- The difficulties of fitting the QTF to repositories based on commissioned resources, and to textbooks, experienced by Tveisme (NDLA) and Varkonyi (Open Textbooks), indicate a need to represent more clearly the target population for the QTF, and to consider the need to change the QTF to provide better support for such repositories.
- Most respondents saw increased transparency itself as the main improvement to practice.

3) Please provide feedback on the level of detail.

3.a: Which new (sub)categories are needed to describe the quality practice that are currently missing in the framework?

Varkonyi (Open Textbooks) thought that the level of detail was fine, and that the checklists were useful. Tveisme (NDLA) identified no problems.

Timm (Wirlernen) reiterated his request for “Metadata, and automated / machine driven quality processes, whether AI or not” and “How the QA concept and criteria were developed”. Istrate (Digitaledu) reiterated that “maybe there should be a special section” on the pedagogical layer.

Ebner (TU Graz) said that “The training fits a little awkwardly, it is rather complex in our case, there is a lot to explain. Maybe the form should ask to provide the process in more detail”. Breustedt (ORCA.nrw) said that “In our case the partners play a big role prior to the upload, that might be an additional category”.

3.b: Which questions can be merged/dropped?

None were identified except by Breustedt (ORCA.nrw), who pointed out that “The questions on methods and instruments are related, I’m not sure this is the best way to differentiate them. Could the methods be represented and linked to the related instruments”.

3.c: Which questions are unclear and need to be better defined?

Timm (Wirlernen) asked “What is ‘official’?”

Tveisme (NDLA) was unclear what a ‘benchmark’ is in this context.

Breustedt (ORCA.nrw) commented that rather than “Who is involved in the QA of your OER repository” she would say “... the OER provided by your repository” if that is what is intended.

Findings for post-QTF completion, question 3:

- The requests for subcategories matched the comments on the dimensions of quality in post-QTF completion 1a above (which should be considered in any future major revision of the QTF).
- Clarification is needed on ‘official’, ‘benchmark’ and ‘QA of your repository’.

4) Please provide feedback on the target group.

4.a: Which target group is the QTF helpful for?

Varkonyi (Open Textbooks), Tveisme (NDLA), Breustedt (ORCA.nrw) emphasised the helpfulness for the repositories who complete the process. Breustedt emphasised that

“it would be very helpful for younger repositories to have easy access to information about well-established repositories.”

Breustedt also identified that users who don't trust a repository won't use it, “and information about QA helps to build that trust”. Similarly Timm (Wirlernen) explained that “in our case we export our materials. The state media centres distribute content in the state... they maintain school clouds, and they need quality assurance... the more clarity on the quality process they receive the better. Internationally, transparency of quality would be valuable, if we want to include their data in our repository”. Ebner (TU Graz) identified that the beneficiaries are “in the end teachers to understand why QA is running and why it is needed”.

Ebner (TU Graz) also emphasised policy makers and those responsible for OER at universities, while Istrate (Digital Edu) singled out “Decision makers in Ministries of Education, providers who build repositories, researchers, funding bodies”.

4.b: Differentiate the QTF for different user groups (e.g. autonomous learners, producers of OER, teachers, ...)? Name the user groups you would differentiate the QTF for.

Breustedt (ORCA.nrw) said she would not differentiate the QTF, as “It is a presentation issue rather than an information content issue”.

All the other respondents thought that the QTF should be differentiated. Istrate (Digitaledu) stated that “Providers and users need different information to be gathered”. Varkonyi (Open Textbooks) noted that teachers are very busy, and “need to be as fast as possible in assessing something for quality”. Tveisme (NDLA) agreed that “You need more detail for people actually working with OER, while teachers would like an overview that they can get into quickly”. Timm (Wirlernen) argued that an automated process may not be relevant to teachers, while authors need to understand the metadata they need to provide. Ebner had the same opinion, as “[p]roviders have to provide infrastructure, teachers provide content, so they have a different experience”.

The question is ambiguous, in that it is not clear if it refers to differentiation in data gathering or in presentation, or both. The answers suggest that most respondents were primarily thinking of presentation, but in the case of Istrate (Digitaledu) the opposite is true. In other cases respondents may have been thinking of both aspects. In any event, it is clear that “Profiling the representation of the quality process.”, as Timm (Wirlernen) described it, would be welcomed by most respondents. Further analysis and consultation

should be carried out before profiling the instrument itself, and the data gathering process.

Findings for post-QTF completion, question 4:

- Three groups of beneficiaries from the QTF were identified (those responsible for the QA of repositories; the users of the content; managers and decision makers).
- Profiling the representation of the quality process would be welcomed by most respondents.

5) Is there anything else you want to add?

Timm (Wirlernen) and Tveisme (NDLA) had no additional comments.

Varkonyi (Open Textbooks) commented that while quality is very important, there is a lack of good OER platforms, and that “if there is no platform there is no one to use the information”.

Ebner (TU Graz) said that international collaboration is necessary, and that we need standards at a European level, but there is a lack of commitment to achieve this at institutional level. He pointed to his work in a European alliance a European Alliance <https://www.unite-university.eu/>.

Breustedt (ORCA.nrw) suggested providing a standard representation of the QTF, with a badge, and emphasised the usefulness of the QTF as a training tool.

Istrate (Digitaledu) stated that the QTF approach could meet the urgent need for an overarching framework

Findings for post-QTF completion, question 5:

Respondents noted a lack of strong OER platforms and of international standard, and it was suggested that the QTF could contribute to resolving these challenges.

4. Recommendations

4.1 Recommended changes to the QTF

Completion of the QTF form as it stands did not present any substantial challenges to any of the interviewees. However, a number of improvements were identified and the QTF has been adapted in response to these findings (detailed in the sections above). It is recommended that this be adopted as a new minor release of the QTF.

Some respondents suggested dividing the QTF questionnaire into categories. Those suggested were 'content', 'metadata' and 'pedagogy'. This proposal was considered to be too far-reaching to be resolved in the present revision as it would require community consultation and testing before release. It is recommended that it be considered for the next major release of the QTF.

4.2 Recommendations for valorisation of the QTF

The respondents were positive about the opportunities presented by the QTF for increasing the transparency of repositories' QA practices. The two benefits which transparency offers were seen as, firstly, a measure that could increase trust in repositories and their contents, and secondly as a means of sharing practice between repositories and providing a resource for the development of individual repositories QA practices. Some respondents also saw the QTF as a possible route to an OER repository quality mark or badge. Thus, the interviews suggest that the QTF is successfully addressing its objectives:

- Making the quality practice of an OER repository visible to users, e.g. learners and teachers.
- Enabling repositories to share and jointly develop their quality practices on the base of a shared QTF.
- Enabling repositories to assess their quality practice according to the framework and possibly develop further quality assurance mechanisms mentioned in the framework categories.

For the potential benefits to be realised, the QTF form would need to generate a representation of the repository's QA practice which could be included on the repository website. More ambitiously, some respondents would welcome an infrastructure for comparison between the QTF profiles of repositories. This could take the form of a website which gathers together representations of different repositories QA practices.

The website could provide a webpage for each representation which can be linked to from each repository's webpage, and a facility for browsing the different representations. There was a consensus that these representations of repositories' practices should be profiled for different audiences. Some or all of the groups which were mentioned in the interviews are candidates for the elaboration of profiles. These included those responsible for the QA of repositories; the teachers and learners who use the content; managers and decision makers.

These proposals provide a useful starting point for consideration of the design dimensions of the infrastructure, but not a sufficient basis for making a recommendation for infrastructure. Similarly, the representation of the repositories' profiles requires a substantial design effort.

The main challenges that respondents reported in completing the QTF form concerned the intellectual difficulty of relating complex local QA processes to a standard framework, and the conversation with the interviewer greatly helped in clarifying their questions. This suggests that the QTF could be most effectively deployed in the interview-based format used in this evaluation. It would therefore be helpful if a future QTF service had funding to support this activity. This seems feasible, as the total number of OER repositories is not very large (for example Santos et al.⁶, in a major survey of 2017, examined 110).

A constraint on the valorisation of the QTF is that it is not equally appropriate for all types of repositories. Of the six repositories interviewed, two felt that the QTF was a valuable initiative but not very relevant to their particular circumstances. Specifically, this was the case for NDLA, which is based on commissioned resources, and Open Textbooks, which uses an editorial process to assure quality, and is also primarily designed to serve the needs of a particular institution. Future valorisation efforts should consider the option of representing more clearly the target repositories for the QTF, and/or changing the QTF to provide better support for such repositories.

⁶ Santos-Hermosa, G., Ferran-Ferrer, N., & Abadal, E. (2017). Repositories of Open Educational Resources: An Assessment of Reuse and Educational Aspects. *The International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 18(5). <https://doi.org/10.19173/irrodl.v18i5.3063>

Appendices

Appendix 1: Informed consent form

INFORMATION DOCUMENT FOR PARTICIPANTS IN THE STUDY ENTITLED ENCORE+ STUDY OF CREDENTIALING OF LEARNING WITH OER

Before returning this consent document, please read carefully the following description of the research activity as a whole, and the pilot session that you have been invited to participate in. Please ask any questions that you may have about it.

The session will be conducted by and is scheduled for

Date:

Place / link:

Time:

Description

You have been invited to participate in the Pilot Study of the ENCORE+ Quality Transparency Framework. The framework was developed by the ENCORE+ project (<https://encoreproject.eu/>), which aims at supporting uptake of and innovation with Open Educational Resources for education and business. The framework has two main purposes:

- To make the quality practice of an OER repository visible to users (e.g. learners and teachers), and to enable repositories to share and jointly develop their quality practices.
- To enable repositories to assess their quality practice according to the framework and possibly develop further the quality assurance mechanisms mentioned in the framework categories.

An ENCORE+ team member will guide you through the Quality Transparency Framework, agreeing and recording responses and comments in a shared document, visible to you. While you go through the Quality Transparency Framework, please bear in mind the following questions:

- 1) Which questions can be merged/dropped?
- 2) Which new (sub)categories are needed to describe the quality practice that are currently missing in the QTF?
- 3) Does the description to the questions provide enough guidance?
- 4) Which questions need to be better defined/explained?

Having gone through the quality framework, you will be asked to respond to some questions about you experienced the process, which will also be recorded in the collaborative document.

We expect that the whole process will take no longer than 60 minutes, with no requirement for any preparation or follow-up activities.

The text generated in the collaborative document will be used in the authoring of a report to the European Commission on the piloting of the Quality Transparency Framework, and may also be used in an academic paper describing the development and evaluation of the Framework. Your participation will be credited with your name, institution and repository, as will any sections of the interview cited in the text.

This research has been approved by the Comité Ética de la Universidad Internacional de la Rioja (Ref. PI004/2023).

Terms of your participation:

- You should be clear that your participation is completely **voluntary**.
- You can withdraw from the study at any time during the pilot session, or subsequently up to the point that the report is published, without providing any explanation, and without negative consequences.
- The information which has been gathered will be used exclusively for the specific purposes of the study.
- You will not receive any financial compensation for your participation.
- You have the right not to answer any particular question.
- You will receive a copy of this document, and have access to the shared document, and all reports and papers which make use of the text as a source of information.

Risks

No risks have been identified in relation to your participation in this study

Benefits

For society: Repositories can make use of the validated quality transparency framework to establish a better relationship with users, and enhanced reliability of repository contents.

For you: guided use of the Quality Transparency Framework may provide insight into the repository for which you are responsible, and guide future work.

Contact information

If you have any questions about this session and its scheduling, would like more information, or have any concerns after the session, please contact Professor Dai Griffiths:

Email: david.griffiths@unir.net

Mobile: 00 34 687 955

Appendix 2. The revised ENCORE+ Quality Transparency Framework

ID	Category	Vocabulary	Description	Mandatory
1. Quality practice				
1.1	Short description of quality practice (Please summarize in a few sentences or bullet points the quality practice for your OER repository.)	N.A.	The summary of your quality practice should provide a short overview. <i>Orientation points:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Describe the lifecycle of an OER from upload to download (how does the upload work, who is involved, how is the OER stored, how is it findable, how can it be downloaded, can it be re-uploaded?). • <u>Briefly</u>, describe (or link to) the quality process of your repository. 	mandatory
1.2	Quality methods in use (Which methods do you use to assess or develop the quality of the OER stored on your repository?)	<input type="checkbox"/> 1. Peer review of new resources (unpaid) <input type="checkbox"/> 2. Peer review of new resources (paid) <input type="checkbox"/> 3. Periodic expert review of repository <input type="checkbox"/> 4. User ranking/rating of OER	If you have any comments on the quality methods you identify, you can add them here. Please start your comment with the number to the side of the relevant check box. <i>Note: in an implementation of the framework, links should be provided to a comment field for each item. The field should accept web links.</i>	non-mandatory

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> 5. Author identification/validation <input type="checkbox"/> 6. Quality-check of metadata <input type="checkbox"/> 7. Application of standardized quality criteria to assess OER <input type="checkbox"/> 8. AI driven <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Collecting user feedback in the repository <input type="checkbox"/> 10. Collecting user feedback in the resources <input type="checkbox"/> 11. Quality through connection to and reputation of institution <input type="checkbox"/> 12. Technical quality parameters (e.g. guaranteed permanent URL of OER) <input type="checkbox"/> 13. Other: ... 		
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1.2.1	Related quality instruments (What instruments do you use to deploy your quality assurance methods?)	<input type="checkbox"/> 1. Author training <input type="checkbox"/> 2. Guidelines for content creation <input type="checkbox"/> 3. Checklist <input type="checkbox"/> 4. Questionnaire <input type="checkbox"/> 5. Handbook <input type="checkbox"/> 6. Benchmarks <input type="checkbox"/> 7. Compliance check with software <input type="checkbox"/> 8. Metadata <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Other: ...	List here the specific tools that the quality assurance methods are translated into, such as a set of guidelines, checklists, material, etc. A benchmark is a statistical basis for a decision to delete a resource or not (e.g. used in past five years, satisfaction rating of 4.3... etc.) <i>Example:</i> <i>If you ensure the quality of your OER repository through the method of author training, link here to the instrument you use. Please start your response with the number to the side of the corresponding checkbox.</i> <i>e.g. the training lesson or material the authors of the OER are trained with. If you ensure quality through peer review, link here to the peer review instruments, e.g. the checklist/guidelines the peer reviewers have to follow when assessing material.</i>	non-mandatory
1.3	Actors involved in quality development (Who is involved in the quality assurance of your OER repository?)	<input type="checkbox"/> User (Teacher) <input type="checkbox"/> User (Learner) <input type="checkbox"/> User (Librarian) <input type="checkbox"/> User (Author) <input type="checkbox"/> User (OER provider) <input type="checkbox"/> User (Other: ...)	Select the actors involved in the quality assurance processes of your OER repository, e.g. users of the repository, or repository officials (i.e. actors explicitly appointed by the repository). When teachers are also authors, both boxes should be ticked. Please, use this comments field to add any necessary	mandatory

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Official (Editorial Board Member) <input type="checkbox"/> Official (CEO) <input type="checkbox"/> Official (Manager) <input type="checkbox"/> Official (Quality Manager) <input type="checkbox"/> Official (Researcher) <input type="checkbox"/> Official (Policy maker) <input type="checkbox"/> Official (Repository developer) <input type="checkbox"/> Official (Technology/infrastructure provider) <input type="checkbox"/> Official (AI services provider) <input type="checkbox"/> Official (Other: ...) <input type="checkbox"/> Other: ... 	<p>explanation of how the roles in the checklist map onto your own circumstances.</p> <p><i>Examples:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Peer review by editorial board consisting of researchers</i> • <i>user rating of content by learners, teachers and authors</i> • <i>hosting of the repository by infrastructure provider</i> • <i>maintenance of the repository by university librarians</i> 	
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ID	Category	Vocabulary	Description	Mandatory
2. Information about your repository				
2.1	Target group (How do you define your target group?)	N.A.	Do you have a clear definition of your target group? Please think about educational systems, subject areas, and user groups profiles.	mandatory
2.2	Legal requirements (What legal requirements do you follow in your repository?)	N.A.	This information helps to compare practice across jurisdictions. <i>Example: GDPR-compliant, compliant with Youth Protection Act, copyright law, ...</i>	non-mandatory
2.3	Personal data (What personal data do you store on the users of your repository?)		<i>Note: consider making this mandatory</i>	non-mandatory
2.3	Repository Language(s)	Language(s) the repository is accessible in	Which language(s) is the OER repository (user interface) accessible in?	mandatory
2.4	OER Language(s)	Language(s) the OER on the repositories is accessible in	Which language(s) are the stored OER offered in? If possible, name the ratio (e.g. 80% English content, 20% German content).	non-mandatory

3. Further aspects				
ID	Category	Vocabulary	Description	Mandatory
3.1	Other (Are there any other quality assurance aspects of your repository that you have not yet mentioned?)	N.A.		non-mandatory

4. Additional services and characteristics				
ID	Category	Vocabulary	Description	Mandatory
4.1	Community integration (Is there a user community associated with your repository)	N.A.	<p>What brings your community together? Does your repository have roles or activities to support the community? What kind of participation in the repository processes (if any) do you offer to community members?</p> <p><i>Examples:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>The OER repository addresses higher education institutions in Southern Germany.</i> • <i>The user community is integrated through a forum.</i> 	non-mandatory

4.2	Credentialing (Does your repository offer/issue any credentials for its community, e.g. for learners, authors, experts, ...)	<input type="checkbox"/> Microcredentials <input type="checkbox"/> Badges for learners <input type="checkbox"/> Badges for authors <input type="checkbox"/> Other: ...	<i>Examples:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Microcredentials are offered to learners for completing a set of multiple OER (like a curriculum).</i> • <i>Content creators can get badges/achievements for uploading OER to the repository.</i> • <i>Users can get badges/achievements/level-ups for rating or reviewing OER.</i> 	non-mandatory
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5. Organizational Data				
ID	Category	Vocabulary	Description	Mandatory
5.1	Name of repository	N.A.	Give here the name of your repository (and acronym if there is one)	mandatory
5.2	Repository provider	N.A.	Name here the institution providing the repository.	mandatory
5.3	Address	N.A.	Postal address given on the website	mandatory
5.4	Website	N.A.	Link	mandatory
5.5	Information provided by	N.A.	State your name.	mandatory

Website

For further and updated information about this project please see:

www.encoreproject.eu

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